

DEVELOPMENT OF BICULTURAL PERSONALITY IS A MODERN TREND IN METHODOLOGY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES TEACHING

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With the increasing importance of foreign languages teaching and learning in Uzbekistan, much attention is being paid to language proficiency development. The purpose of communication and language learning are often derived from cultural frameworks that have been in place for centuries and are often assumed to be so basic that they are rarely questioned. Influence of culture and culturally determined constructs on the assumptions associated with interaction, teaching, and learning, and the ways in which the teaching and learning of the target language and culture can be carried out. That's why the matters of forming and development of bicultural individuals is topical nowadays.

The concept of "biculturalism" has been defined by many scholars. Most general explanation of this concept is that biculturalism represents comfort and proficiency with both one's heritage culture and the culture of the country or region in which one has settled. From this perspective, individuals are considered bicultural if they speak both the language of their heritage cultural context and the language has been dealt with in the angle of linguocultural education (Galskova, 2007) or intercultural education (Makhkamova, 2010).

According to Galskova (2007, p.65) the goal and result of any language education should be a second language personality formation which can participate in the intercultural communication. So the question appears: What do we mean by the second language personality? To answer this question we should address to the basic studies related to this term.

By the language personality Karaulov understands the multilayer and multicomponent set of language abilities, skills, readiness to undertake the communicative behaviour in accordance with a certain type of speech activities (1987, p.29). The author distinguishes three levels in language development: the second level presupposes the logic-cognitive development via personality thesaurus (world picture); and the third level is the level of communicative-action needs and intentions (Karaulov, 1987, p.236). In methodology of language teaching the model of second language personality development is associated with two thesauruses where Thesaurus I dates back to the associative network of verbal language and forms the language world picture, while Thesaurus II forms the conceptual or global world picture (Galskova, 2007, p.69). According to Khaleeva, acquiring world picture knowledge means that we enter into cognitive level of language personality (1989). For development of bicultural personality as active participant of meaning and mutual understanding. So the thesaurus of lexicon and thesaurus of conceptual world picture of the native speakers should be taught and learned to be a second language personality or bicultural personality. Developing Thesaurus is a difficult task, because it is related to the process of acculturation via cultural awareness and teaching intercultural competence.

Therefore, to develop <<second language personality>> we should incorporate teaching language and culture "as a set of beliefs, values and behavioral norms shared by community members, serving their self-identity with this social group" (Jalolov & Makhkamova,

2015). Another striking demonstration of this idea we find in the statement of Byram and Morgan: "it is axiomatic in our view that cultural learning has to place as an integral part of language learning, and vice versa" (1994, p.5). At the same time Byram specified that development of language and culture awareness contributes directly to improving language proficiency level (1991, p.22).

Thus, development of bicultural personality is difficult task for language teachers, but they should do it, because violations of cultural norms of appropriateness in interaction between native and non-native speakers often lead to sociopragmatic failure, breakdowns in communication.

Reference:

1. Byram M. Teaching culture and language : Towards an integrated model .// In D. Buitjes & M. Byram (eds.) Mediating language and cultures: Towards an intercultural theory of foreign language education. — Clevedon, UK : Multilingual Matters, 1991. Pp.17-32.
2. Byram M., Morgan C. Teaching -and-learning language-and-culture. — Clevedon , UK : Multilingual Matters, 1994.
3. Jalolov J.J. Makhkamova G.T., Ashurov Sh.S. English Language Teaching Methodology.— T.: Fan va texnologiya, 2015.-336 p.
4. Галскова Н.Д., Н.И.Гез. Теория обучения иностранным языкам: Лингводидактика и методика.— М.: Академия, 2007.
5. Карулов Ю.Н. Русский язык и языковая личность.— М.: Наука, 1987.
6. Махкамова Г.Т. Концепция формирования межкультурной компетенции студентов факультетов английского языка.— Т.: Фан , 2010.
7. Халеева И.И. Основы теории обучения пониманию иноязычной речи (подготовка переводчиков).— М., 1989.